

THE IMPORTANCE OF INFLAMMATORY INDICATORS, C-REACTIVE PROTEIN, AND PRO-INFLAMMATORY CYTOKINES IN THE EVOLUTION AND ADVANCEMENT OF HEART FAILURE POST-INFARCTION

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Achievements in the field of immunology and molecular biology indicate the important role of immune activation and systemic inflammation in the new theory of CHF pathogenesis [1,2,3,9,10]. At present, the pathogenesis of CHF should be considered in the light of modern concepts in the field of cardiology, endocrinology, immunology, and molecular medicine [5,11]. One of the latest achievements of modern cardiology is the establishment of the role of activation of the cytokine system in the pathogenesis of CHF

Purpose of the study: to study the role of inflammatory markers, C-reactive protein and proinflammatory cytokines in the development and progression of postinfarction heart failure.

Material and methods: In our study, when studying the content of pro-inflammatory cytokines in peripheral venous blood: TNF- α and interleukins 1 β and interleukin 6 in patients with functional classes I-IV of chronic heart failure, 60 patients aged 41 to 70 years who had previously undergone AMI were examined. with CHF according to the classification of the New York Heart Association (NYHA).

Conclusions: Analyzing the change in the content of inflammation indicators in the functional classes of heart failure (Table 2.), it should be noted an increase in the content of CRP in patients with CHF I FC by 2.9 times and 4.8-5.3 times in CLE II, III and IV FC. This indicates an increase in the processes of inflammation, starting with II FC CNC and maintaining this increase until the terminal stage of the disease.

As for TNF- α , IL-6, IL-1 β , an increase in their content was noted, starting with patients with CNK FC I. This increase progressed to stage III CNC, for TNF- α and IL-6, and was expressed to a lesser extent compared with the indicators in patients with I-III FC CNC. The content of IL-1 β , in contrast to TNF- α and IL-6, increased in accordance with the severity of chronic circulatory insufficiency and reached maximum levels in patients with IV FC CNK.

The study revealed a negative effect of TNF- α , IL-1 β and IL-6 hypercytokinemia in patients with postinfarction CHF, which plays a key role in the pathogenesis and progression of LV remodeling.

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